

POTENTIOMETRIC STUDIES IN OXIDATION-REDUCTION REACTIONS† PART XIII. OXIDATION WITH POTASSIUM METAPERIODATE

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Mercurous chloride, stannous chloride, arsenious oxide, tartar emetic, hydrazine hydrochloride and potassium sulphocyanide have been estimated by a potentiometric method, using potassium metaperiodate as an oxidising agent.

Singh and Singh (this *Journal*, 1952, 29, 34) have shown that potassium metaperiodate reacts with mercurous chloride, stannous chloride, arsenious oxide, tartar emetic, hydrazine hydrochloride and potassium sulphocyanide in presence of concentrated hydrochloric acid.

The reactions have been utilised in the quantitative determination of these substances by the potentiometric method using potassium metaperiodate as an oxidising agent.

EXPERIMENTAL

Potassium metaperiodate was prepared by the method of Bahl and Singh (*ibid.*, 1940, 17, 167).

Curves 1-6 refer respectively to NH_3 , NH_2HCl , KCNS , SnCl_2 , Hg_2Cl_2 , As_2O_3 and tartar emetic

The oxidation-reduction electrode, which consisted of a bright platinum foil immersed in a solution to be titrated, was coupled with a saturated calomel electrode through an agar-agar potassium chloride bridge. The cell was placed in a water-bath, the temperature of which was maintained at 20°. E.M.F. of the cell was read on a potentiometer.

A known weight of each substance was mixed with water, acidified with concentrated hydrochloric acid and titrated against standard potassium metaperiodate. In these titrations, normality of the solution with respect to hydrochloric acid was kept between 4*N* and 7*N*. The titrations were conducted in an atmosphere of carbon dioxide and the mixture was kept stirred by a mechanical stirrer.

The titrations, one for each substance, are represented by the curves given in Fig. 1.

In these titrations it is evident that with the addition of the titrant the E.M.F. rose steadily till the equivalence point. At the equivalence point there was a sharp jump in the potential, followed by a steady rise in each case.

From the amount of potassium metaperiodate used, corresponding to equivalence point in each titration, the amount of each substance was calculated. In the following table the values obtained are compared with the amounts of the substances taken.

TABLE I

KIO ₄ used.	Hg ₂ Cl ₂		KIO ₄ used.	SnCl ₂	
	taken.	found.		taken.	found.
0.0384 g.	0.2365 g.	0.2369 g.	0.07149 g.	0.2124 g.	0.2107 g.
0.0574	0.3548	0.3541	0.08962	0.2656	0.2642
0.0767	0.4730	0.4735	0.10300	0.3057	0.3037
0.0959	0.5913	0.5919	0.11895	0.3531	0.3507
0.1152	0.7095	0.7101	0.14210	0.4215	0.4184
			0.15575	0.4621	0.4597
	As ₂ O ₃			Tartar emetic.	
0.04198	0.0545	0.0542	0.04450	0.1941	0.1939
0.05731	0.0743	0.0740	0.05931	0.2586	0.2584
0.07678	0.0990	0.0991	0.06820	0.2975	0.2971
0.09564	0.1238	0.1236	0.07998	0.3488	0.3484
0.11492	0.1485	0.1484	0.08907	0.3883	0.3880
0.15311	0.1980	0.1977	0.09781	0.4259	0.4261
0.03845	0.01713	0.01718	0.03290	0.0139	0.0139
0.05762	0.02569	0.02573	0.04350	0.0185	0.0184
0.07659	0.03425	0.03422	0.05456	0.0231	0.0230
0.09564	0.04281	0.04273	0.07112	0.0301	0.0300
0.11481	0.05138	0.05129	0.09353	0.0393	0.0395
0.13398	0.05994	0.05985	0.1150	0.0486	0.0485

The results show that mercurous chloride, stannous chloride, arsenious oxide, tartar emetic, hydrazine hydrochloride and potassium sulphocyanide can be determined directly by the potentiometric method, using potassium metaperiodate as an oxidising agent.